

Optimal Surgical Timing after Neoadjuvant Therapy in Rectal and Breast Cancer: A Narrative Review

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Introduction

Neoadjuvant therapy (NAT) plays an important role in the management of locally advanced rectal and breast cancer, as it aims to downstage the tumor, increase the chance of organ-preservation surgery and provide valuable prognostic information by assessing pathologic complete response (pCR). Although it is widely used in clinical practice, there is still uncertainty regarding the optimal interval time between NAT and definitive surgery. A short interval may limit recovery from therapy-induced toxicity, whereas a prolonged interval may increase the chance of tumor re-growth or malignant spread. This review evaluates the evidence to identify optimal interval time

Materials and methods

A narrative review of the scientific literature was conducted using PubMed (2014–2026). The following keywords were used: “neoadjuvant,” “surgery,” “surgical interval time,” “rectal cancer,” and “breast cancer.” Nineteen relevant studies focusing on the impact of surgical interval time on oncological outcomes were selected and reviewed.

Results

Evidence from recent meta-analyses and clinical audits indicates that, in breast cancer, surgery performed within 4 weeks after completion of chemotherapy is commonly practiced, while delays beyond 8 weeks are associated with less favorable oncological outcomes, including lower pCR rates. In rectal cancer, although a 6–8 week interval remains standard, several studies suggest that extending this to 10–12 weeks may increase pCR rates. However, this potential benefit must be weighed against increased surgical complexity and treatment-related morbidity, with no consistent improvement in survival outcomes. Factors influencing interval selection include patient recovery, diagnostic requirements, technical and biological considerations, and multidisciplinary decision-making.

Conclusion

In breast and rectal cancers, the interval between NAT and surgery must maintain a balance of oncological benefit with patient safety. Overall, timing should not follow a one-size-fits-all approach; instead, it should be targeted individually based on tumor type, treatment response, recovery from toxicity and the patient's overall clinical status.

Keywords

Neoadjuvant therapy, Surgical Interval Time, Rectal Cancer, Breast Cancer